

ISic0619

I.Sicily inscription 0619

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

via Lincoln

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico dei benedettini

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

Edition: EDR071677

1. M (arcus) Iulius M (arci) f (ilius) Pap (iria) Seda
2. tus Narb (one) mil (es) leg (ionis)
3. VII Gem (inae) (F) e (licis) centuria Iuvenis
4. mil (itavit) an (nos) XIII vixit an (nos) XXXII.
5. (H) i (c) p (ositus) .
- 6.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175847

EDR 071677

EDCS 17100042

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1897.0132

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. *Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535.* Warminster. At 359 n.60

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 240-241

Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. ANRW. 2.11.1: 3-89.* At 40

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0619. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385070>